

KINETICS OF THE SAPONIFICATION OF ESTERS IN DILUTE SOLUTIONS. A STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF SUBSTITUTION ON THE RATE-DETERMINING FACTORS.

BY HIRALAL SHRIVASTAVA.

A kinetic study of the saponification of eleven aliphatic esters, $R'COOR$ (where R and R' vary from CH_3 to C_9H_{11}) has been made in pure and dilute aqueous solutions. Analysis of the results on the basis of the equation $K = PZe^{-E/RT}$ shows that changes in velocity are due in a greater measure, if not entirely, to changes in the steric factor. In the case of normal esters, however, the energy of activation shows a slight but progressive increase as the series is ascended, whereas for isomeric esters the energy of activation is practically the same. These observations have been discussed in the light of the results obtained by others.

Kinetic studies of saponification of esters may be traced back for more than half a century. It is, however, only during recent years that a rational study of the subject has been attempted in the light of the application of the equation $K = PZe^{-E/RT}$ in the interpretation of kinetic data. Special attention has been directed to the experimental determination of the energy of activation, (E) as a means towards arriving at a correct understanding of the effect of alkyl substitution on the different rate-determining factors in the saponification of esters.

Earlier work on the subject in pure aqueous solutions (Warder, *Ber.*, 1881, 14, 1361; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1881, 3, 203; Reicher, *Annalen*, 1885, 228, 257; 1885, 232, 103; 1887, 238, 276; Smith and Olsson, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 102, 26; 1925, 118, 99) shows that if we start with CH_3COOR and vary R from C_2H_5 to C_9H_{11} there is no appreciable variation in E (which is practically constant round about 11,000 cal.). More recently Evans, Gordon and Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1439) from their study of the rates of saponification of different esters in 85% alcoholic solutions found that (i) E increases gradually as the normal series is ascended and tends to reach constant maximum, and also (ii) in esters which are not branched at the α -carbon atom the changes in K are due almost entirely to changes in E . These findings have been adversely criticised by Smith and Levenson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1172; also *cf.*, Smith, *ibid.*, p. 254) whose experimental results show no appreciable variation in E as one passes up the ester series. These latter authors contend that variations in K are due entirely to changes in the steric factor P .

In a subsequent paper Smith and McReynolds (*ibid.* p. 1963) have offered an explanation of all observed regularities and abnormalities in these saponification studies on the basis of a ring theory for the structure of higher members.

All inferences and conclusions in these matters obviously depend upon the accuracy of the kinetic measurements and the conditions under which they are made. The investigations referred to above have all been made in reaction mixtures at concentrations convenient for purposes of the usual acidimetric and alkalimetric titrations. This analytical procedure puts a limit to the dilution up to which we can proceed.

It appeared to the author desirable to undertake a study of the kinetics of saponification of a series of esters in very dilute solutions with a view to collecting accurate data and testing the validity of the different views put forward in regard to the influence of substitution on the rate of reaction. The present study deals with kinetic measurements of the saponification of eleven esters.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation and Purification of Esters.

Ethyl propionate, *n*-propyl acetate, isopropyl acetate and butyl acetate were prepared by Fischer-Speier's method from the corresponding (Kahlbaum's) alcohols and acids. Other esters were purchased from Kahlbaum. Each ester was shaken with a slight excess of dilute sodium carbonate solution to remove any acid present, then washed with pure water, and dried thoroughly by shaking with anhydrous sodium sulphate and leaving overnight. The purified and dried ester was repeatedly distilled. In the case of low boiling esters, an eighteen-inch fractionating column was used. In every case the middle fraction distilling over at a constant head temperature was collected for experimental work. The observed boiling points are recorded below. The figures within brackets indicate the corresponding pressures in mm. of mercury :—Methyl acetate, 56.2° (738.40); ethyl acetate, 76.0° (735.65); *n*-propyl acetate, 100.5° (739.35); isopropyl acetate, 88.0° (734.15); *n*-butyl acetate, 125.0° (739.35); isoamyl acetate 137.5° (738.70); methyl propionate, 78.5° (738.70); ethyl propionate, 98.0° (734.15); methyl butyrate, 101.0° (735.35); ethyl butyrate, 118.5° (735.35); ethyl isovalerate, 133.2° (736.20).

The purified esters were analysed by leaving overnight a weighed sample of each ester in contact with a known excess of standard alkali in well stoppered Jena glass flasks, and then titrating the excess of alkali with standard acid. All the esters gave satisfactory proof of purity (between 99.5 and 100%).

Analytical Procedure and other Experimental Details.

The saponification was studied in aqueous potassium hydroxide solutions at three or four temperatures for each ester. An electrically controlled water thermostat was used and the temperature could be kept constant to ± 0.01 of a degree. All solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Vessels used were of Jena or pyrex glass.

The main difference between previous studies and this one is chiefly in regard to the dilution at which measurements have been made, dilution herein employed being in the region of $0.005N$ to $0.001N$.

The reaction was followed by pipetting out known volumes of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and running it into a known quantity of hydrochloric acid solution. This stopped the reaction, the acid catalysed hydrolysis being comparatively very slow. The excess of acid was estimated by adding to the mixture potassium iodide and potassium iodate and titrating the iodine liberated against standard (nearly $0.005N$) sodium thiosulphate solution. This iodometric method, as is well known, is capable of yielding accurate results and has enabled us to extend our studies to the region of great dilutions.

In the case of low boiling esters the reaction mixture was made up by diluting 25 c.c. of $0.04N$ -potassium hydroxide solution to 225 c.c. with conductivity water, and then adding in 25 c.c. of a freshly prepared ester solution of known concentration (in the neighbourhood of $0.04N$) at the required temperature. In order to reduce to a minimum losses due to evaporation, the ester solution was prepared as follows: a 100 c.c. measuring flask was filled with water to within a short distance of the mark on the neck. The ester was then added and dissolved by shaking well. Only a few drops of water were then needed to dilute the solution to the mark. In the case of high boiling esters, the ester was directly added to the alkali solution at the required temperature from an accurately calibrated micro-pipette.

At least two, and usually three or four runs were made at each temperature for each ester.

The bimolecular velocity constant was calculated in terms of litres/g. mols. min. from the equation

$$\log K = \frac{2.303}{i(a-b)} \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

R E S U L T S.

The results of a typical run are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Saponification of ethyl acetate at 25°.

($N/252.29$ ester + $N/250.1$ KOH); $(a-b) = 0.181$ c.c. $N/208.22$; $(a-x)$ and $(b-x)$ are expressed in c.c. $N/208.22$.

Time (<i>t</i>)	Alkali conc. ($a-x$)	Ester conc. ($b-x$)	Velocity constant, <i>K</i> . (in litres/g. mols. min.)
0 min.	16.875	16.694	—
4	15.85	15.669	5.4606
9	14.675	14.494	5.3685
15	13.425	13.244	5.4713
22	12.20	12.019	5.5301
32	10.90	10.719	5.4225
			Mean 5.4500

TABLE II.

Effect of variation in initial concentration of alkali and ester on the velocity constant for the ethyl acetate by aqueous KOH at 28°.

Initial conc. of KOH.	Initial conc. of ester.	K_{28}° (litres/g. mols. min.).
0.004 <i>N</i>	0.005 <i>N</i>	6.89
„	0.00125	6.72
0.0025	0.005	6.825
„	0.0025	6.865
0.002	0.005	6.818
0.001	0.010	6.355
„	0.005	6.22
„	0.002	6.16
„	0.001	5.87

The figures in Table II show that when the initial concentrations of the reactants are altered over a narrow range (*cf.* figures in the first five horizontal rows) there is no appreciable change in *K*. This result is in

agreement with the observations of previous workers (Arrhenius, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1887, 1, 110; Burgarsky, *ibid.*, 1891, 8, 398). The last four sets of figures (horizontal rows) show, however, that when the concentration of KOH is kept constant and the initial concentration of ester varied from 0.01M to 0.001M, the value of K falls by about 10%. Changes of such magnitude are usually met with in reactions taking place between neutral molecules and ions and an increase in K with an increase in the initial concentration of the non-electrolyte is from general considerations attributable to increase in the activity of the reacting ion. The evidence for such a view should, however, be regarded as qualitative (Moran and Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1620; Kappanna and Shrikhande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 557) and the point has not been further pursued in this investigation.

Table III gives the values of K for different esters at different temperatures. These are the results of experiments carried out with different esters, the initial concentration of each reactant in the different reaction mixtures being in the neighbourhood of $M/250$. The results with different esters, therefore, relate strictly to comparable conditions—a point of importance from the standpoint of the present investigation.

Table IV contains the values of K at 25° for each ester together with the corresponding values of E , Z , PZ and P . The energies of activation were calculated from the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$. Z was calculated from the usual kinetic theory formula in terms of litres/g. mols. min.. For this purpose the molecular diameters, σ , were calculated from Sugden's parachor values by means of the formula $\sigma = 0.725 \times 10^{-8} \times (\text{Parachor})$. The values of PZ and P were then calculated from the formula $K = PZe^{-E/RT}$.

TABLE III.

Ester.	K_{25} .	K_{30} .	K_{35} .	K_{40} .	K_{45} .	K_{55} .
Methyl acetate	8.889	11.92	15.41	19.75		
Methyl propionate	7.203	10.00	13.55	18.09		
Methyl butyrate	4.860	6.456	8.902	—	14.48	24.60
Ethyl acetate	5.454	—	9.448	—	16.18	28.24
Ethyl propionate	4.588	—	8.123	—	14.015	
Ethyl butyrate	2.405	—	4.573	—	7.874	13.22
Ethyl isovalerate	0.871	—	1.487	—	2.397	3.818
<i>n</i> -Propyl acetate	4.474	—	8.054	—	13.82	
<i>iso</i> Propyl acetate	1.383	—	2.462	—	4.394	
Butyl acetate	3.863	—	7.028	—	12.11	
<i>iso</i> Amyl acetate	3.195	—	5.836	—	9.241	15.80

TABLE IV.

Ester.	K_{25} .	E .	$Z \times 10^{-8}$.	$PZ \times 10^{-8}$.	P .
Methyl acetate	8.889	10000	1.2474	1.8769	1.547
Ethyl acetate	5.454	10250	1.3817	1.7418	1.2624
<i>n</i> -Propyl acetate	4.474	10550	1.3987	2.3922	1.7095
<i>iso</i> Propyl acetate	1.383	10800	1.3759	1.1268	0.8189
Butyl acetate	3.863	10800	1.3977	3.1471	2.2517
<i>iso</i> Amyl acetate	3.195	10060	2.1586	0.7406	0.3447
Methyl propionate	7.203	11150	1.3856	10.744	7.777
Ethyl propionate	4.588	10400	1.3899	1.928	1.387
Methyl butyrate	4.860	10500	1.8666	2.3559	1.263
Ethyl butyrate	2.405	10700	1.7127	1.712	1.0451
Ethyl isovalerate	0.871	9600	2.1442	0.09376	0.0437

An examination of these tables reveals the following points:—

(a) K is of the same order of magnitude thus showing that the mechanism of saponification reaction is the same for different esters.

(b) K decreases at first rapidly, then slowly as the homologous series is ascended, and the value of E , in general, shows a progressive increase. But the drop in K in passing from methyl (or ethyl) propionate to methyl (or ethyl) butyrate is much greater than the decrease in K in passing from methyl (or ethyl) acetate to methyl (or ethyl) propionate. But there is no corresponding discrepancy between the values of K for ethyl, *n*-propyl, and butyl acetates; decrease in K is regular if the alcohol radical is changed.

(c) Isomeric normal esters are saponified at much the same rate; but the *iso*- isomer is saponified much more slowly than the *n*- isomer. The value of E for all isomeric esters is the same within experimental error.

(d) The value of the steric factor, P , is much smaller for esters branched at the α -carbon atom than for the normal esters, and this is paralleled by the lower values of K for these branched chain esters.

D I S C U S S I O N .

The independence of K of the initial concentration of either the ester or the alkali indicates that the reaction is a straight forward bimolecular

reaction taking place in accordance with the generally accepted mechanism for alkaline hydrolysis of esters,

It is assumed that the hydroxyl ion gets attached to the carboxyl carbon atom with the simultaneous transfer of the negative charge on to the carbonyl oxygen and the transition complex so obtained then decomposes to give the reaction products.

As the life of this transition complex is assumed to be short, the rate of reaction is determined by the rate of formation of this complex. Hence the decrease in the value of K on ascending the homologous series leads to the conclusion that as R and R' increase in size, the formation of the intermediate complex is retarded by some means. But as the value of Z does not vary appreciably with increasing length of carbon chain, this retardation may be due either to an increase in the energy of activation or to greater screening of the carboxyl group from the approach of the hydroxyl ion due to spatial disposition of the substituents R and R' or to both.

Comparatively low values of P for the esters, branched at the α -carbon atom, show that in these cases at least, it is the steric factor which is responsible for the low velocities of saponification. Evans and co-workers attribute this to the formation of a hydrogen bond between the carbonyl oxygen and the β -carbon atom of the alkyl chain (which does not influence E perceptibly) simultaneously with the approach of the negative hydroxyl ion. This seems to be the most plausible explanation. The hydrogen bond leads to the completion of a five-membered ring and the formation of this ring naturally decreases the solid angle for the approach of hydroxyl ions to the carboxyl carbon, and thus decreases the rate of formation of the transition complex which determines K .

The formation of a similar ring structure in the butyric acid molecule (as has been suggested already by Smith and others) would offer an easy explanation of the observation that the difference between the values of K for methyl (or ethyl) propionate and methyl (or ethyl) butyrate is much larger than the difference between the values of K for methyl (or ethyl) acetate and methyl (or ethyl) propionate.

In the case of normal esters also the value of PZ changes from ester to ester, but at the same time a progressive, though slight, increase in the value of E with increasing chain length is at once evident from the

results tabulated above. It may be argued that these variations may be only apparent and may be easily accounted for by slight experimental errors as in fact almost all the values of E lie within the range 10400 ± 400 cal. But it is somewhat remarkable that the increase is almost regular. This makes it desirable to take into account the variations in K from ester to ester.

The general conclusion is that the length and structure of the carbon chain in alkyl esters may have an effect not only on the steric factor but also on the energy of activation. In the case of early members of normal alkyl esters, variation in K seems to be due not only to a change in the steric factor but also to a progressive increase in the energy of activation. But in the case of esters branched at the α -carbon atom, the steric factor seems to be predominant. Hinshelwood and Legard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 587, 1588) demonstrated that substitution in the α -position often caused an increase in the activation energy. While this was found to be the case for the ethyl ester of *isovaleric acid* (amongst those of some other acids) studied by Evans and coworkers, the present work, in fact, shows a decrease in the value of E for ethyl *isovalerate*.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
NAGPUR.

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